

Ayurvedic *Maharasas*, the Repository of Primordial Organic Chemistry

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A fundamental problem of tracing the sequence of primordial organic chemistry is the identification of the primitive organic molecules, from among the currently known millions of possible compounds. The observed intimate association, for ages, of a selected group of organic compounds, e.g. hydroxyacetophenones and oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones (DBPs), and of the Ayurvedic *maharasas* (inorganic minerals), in their natural habitats, is regarded as a strong circumstantial evidence in support of an organized sequence of primordial organic chemistry. These phenolic compounds also occur, selectively and consistently within the core of 'till' and boulders of the Gangotri-glacier (1 to 60 million-year-old). Another unique feature of these compounds is that the DBPs are found in the organ deposits of several insects (baemolymph gland), animals (scent-gland, clover-stone), and in man (kidney and gall stone), but rarely so in plants. This phenomenon suggests their non-photosynthetic (abiotic) origin, at least partly, which is also supported from their high $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values. These organic compounds seem to bear a link between the primordial and the modern eras of organic chemistry on earth.

Ayurvedic *maharasas*

Ayurvedic *maharasas*¹, a group of eight metallo-rasayanas (panacea), are used to promote health and longevity and to treat incurable diseases in man. According to the Ayurvedic texts¹, these are inorganic minerals. The names of the *maharasas*, their respective mineral constituents and metal ion compositions in parenthesis, are as follows: *Abhraka* (biotite, Mg, Fe, Al; muscovite, K, Al, Fe, Mg); *Vaikranta* (manganite, Mn, Co, V); *Makshika* (*rajata*-variety, pyrite, Fe; *svarna*-variety, chalcopyrite, Cu, Fe); *Vimala* (pyrites, Fe, Cu, Ni, Co, As); *Sasyaka* (chalcenthite, Fe, Cu); *Chapala* (bismuthite, Bi, Fe, Sn, Cu, Sb); *Rasaka* (or *Kharpara*, calamine, Zn; willemite, Zn, Si); and *Shilajit* (fresh and paleohumus complex of Fe, Cu, Zn, Mg, Ca, Mo, Ti, Al)².

Inorganic minerals would have predominated on the primitive earth as they do now³. Minerals of around colloidal dimensions (*ca.* 1/256 mm diam.), e.g. clays and equivalent minerals which constitute the main ingredients of the *maharasas* would have formed continuously by an energetically downhill process from solutions derived from rock weathering. The resultant energy-rich minerals accumulated in rock veins and sedimentary ore mines eventually constituted the 'apparatus' and the 'reagents' for primordial and progressive organic syntheses. These natural habitats of the inorganic minerals consequently formed ecological niche of the primitive microorganisms of wide morphological and chemical diversities.

But the question remains as to how these primitive organisms have originated and remain extant in the mineral deposits? Also, what are the primitive organic compounds one can find preserved within the mineral bodies and among the associated microorganisms from which one can reconstitute primordial organic chemistry? How one can think of

bio-organic chemistry without enzymes? These questions are now addressed and answers partly obtained by using combination of disciplines necessary to delve into the secrets of organic chemistry of the remote era. The speculations and evidence generated from contemporary-current researches are depicted in this article.

Early metabolists

According to currently accepted tenets, life at an early stage of evolution was autotrophic and the associated organic reactions were autocatalytic⁴. The organic reactions were confined to an essentially two-dimensional monomolecular layer on a solid surface, such as clay mineral of colloidal dimensions. The minerals controlled the organic reactions involving CO_2/CO , H_2O , NH_3 , H_2S , and photons (energy from light). The organic compounds thus generated constituted the building blocks (precursors) of the early metabolists, the metabolons. The metabolons were capable of growth and metabolism and were on the direct ancestral line of the proto-organisms that eventually took over the genetic control.

Some years ago, in delving into the chemistry of *Shilajit*, the foremost of the *maharasas*, Ghosal *et al.*² considered Scheme 1 as the central thesis of chemical evolution of life on earth. An intermediate (Scheme 2, str. **la, b**) considered

(i) Clay mineral catalysis/hv; (ii) Formose reaction to microorganics, (iii) humus-metabolon transitions, (iv) genetic take-over, (v) progressive evolution

Scheme 1 Prebiotic organic synthesis on clay minerals^{2-4,6}

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to be involved in this pathway contains plethora of poly-anionic surface binders, e.g. carboxylate, phosphate and enate ions, which get attached to earth's cationic solid surfaces⁴, containing complex pyrites and congener minerals

Fig. 1. Phenolic compounds isolated from *maharasas*-minerals and from stone-pebbles (Gangotri-glacier), for expression of R¹, R², R³ and a-c, see Table 1.

TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTION PATTERNS OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS OCCURRING IN MAHARASA-MINERALS AND IN STONE-PEBBLES*

Struct no **	Substitution		
	R ¹	R ²	R ³
2a	H	H	—
b	OH	H	—
c	OH	OH	—
3a	OH	H	H
b	OH	OH	H
c	OH	OH	OH
4a	H	—	—
b	Fatty O-acyl	—	—
5a	H	H	—
b	H	OH	—
c	Me	OH	—

*Collected from Gangotri glacier **For structures, see Fig 1

Scheme 2. Abiotic sequence of formation of phenolic compounds. 1a, carbon-carbon anionic intermediates bonded to cationic clay mineral surface, (i) aldol, (ii) Claisen; (iii) Michael; (iv) Diels-Alder type reactions; 1b, poly- β -keto-anionic intermediate

(e.g. biotite, muscovite, willemite) en route to a large variety of phenolic end-products (Scheme 2). These phenolic compounds (Fig. 1, str. 2-5) have been consistently found to occur in the humic substances of the *maharasas*^{2,5}.

Further support for the notion of the primitive origin of these phenolic compounds (2-5) is obtained from a circumstantial evidence. These compounds have been found to occur within the inner core of the terminal moraine (till) and boulders of the Gangotri glacier⁶. These siliceous bodies contain appreciable amounts of organic compounds surrounding their finely crystalline silica core. Optical microscopy of thin sections of the pebbles showed light-brown streaks of organic deposits, distributed in laminations parallel to the bedding planes. The inner-surface distribution and complexation of the organic compounds indicate their original sedimentary deposition characteristic, that is prior to the compaction of the surrounding siliceous matrix. The ground mass of the rock-till was greyish in appearance. X-Ray powder data revealed the presence of quartz, feldspar and pyrites in association with clay particles. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the pebbles showed spheroidal or elliptical voids in the inner matrix structures in which the organic complexes were embedded. Determinations of the concentration of K and the Rb/Sr ratio suggested the age of the rock materials to be well beyond 1 million years.

In a typical experiment, the organic materials were partially dissociated from the organo-mineral laminar surfaces by repeated trituration with organic solvents of graded polarity. Hptlc and hplc analyses of the corresponding organic solvent extractives showed⁶ the presence of all the phenolic compounds drawn in Fig. 1. An inner-section of the pebble was dipped in hydrofluoric acid, the acid-treated material was washed with water, dried and pulverized. An aqueous suspension of the pulverized material was trituated with Dowex-50 resin and the effluent was successively extracted with ethyl acetate and n-butanol. The residues from the organic solvent extractives were silylated and then subjected to gc-ms analyses. These determinations established the presence of the phenolic compounds (Fig. 1), among other oligomeric phenolic complexes (hptlc).

When the polyalkenyl/alkyl- β -keto intermediate, produced from a surface reaction of the type shown in Scheme 1, attains a favourable transition state ring size (Scheme 2, str. 1b), quasi-intramolecular condensations (i-iii) would take place to form the thermodynamically favourable aromatic ring structures (Fig. 1, str. 2-5). The ring compounds, being detached from the clay mineral surface, would produce 'organized' complex structures, e.g. the metallo-(ferrato)humate complexes (Fig. 2, str. 6 and 7), which

would remain in intimate association with the rhizospheric clay minerals as stable complexes.

Humus, the epitome of the maharasas

Comprehensive chromatographic, spectroscopic and chemical analyses^{2,5} of the *maharasas* (*vide infra*) showed the presence of a large number of low mol. wt. (M_w) humic intermediates (lipids, amino acids, and phenolics; Fig. 1)⁷ and also medium and high M_w humic complexes (Fig. 2) as strikingly common ingredients. Humus thus seems to be the epitome of not one (*Shilajit*)² but all the *maharasas*⁵. The stability of the *maharasas* is due, primarily, to complexation with the transition metal ions which produce stable free-radical-containing resonance-stabilized metallohumate complexes (Fig. 2, str. 6a — 6b). Additionally, due to the presence of a large number of phenolic hydroxyl, carboxylic, carbonyl ligand functions in the fulvic acids (FAs) of the humus, and the tenacious association of aquo-donor groups with siliceous materials, stable *maharasa*-complex formation of the type 7 (Fig. 2) is a distinct possibility. Indeed, these complexes have been detected in the humic constituents of *Abhraka*, *Makshika* and *Shilajit*^{5,6}.

According to currently accepted tenets⁷⁻⁹, humus formation is a two-stage process : (1) bio- and geochemical decomposition of the components of flora (plants and epiphytes of terrestrial, aquatic, and arboreal origin) into low M_w compounds, and (2) polymerization and heteropolycondensation of the degraded monomeric units from process (1) into medium- and high- M_w entities. The medium and high M_w compounds thus formed, on further interaction, e.g. chelation and molecular association with metal ions and rhizospheric minerals, produce stable organomineral complexes (strs. 6 and 7) — the common molecular architecture of the *maharasas*^{9,10}.

Fig. 2. Humate-clay mineral/metal ion complex : (L) = oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones, hydroxyacetophenones, phenolic acids and/or aquo-ligands, (FAs) = fulvic acids; dotted line denotes C-C, C-O, C-N substitution by heteropolycondensation and/or carboxyl function arising out of oxidation, and (C) = clay mineral

Humus and abiogenesis

The significance of humus in the replication, growth, and maintenance of biological systems via synthesis of organic molecules has not been evaluated until recently. A universal scheme of vast dimension has been revealed during the study of the chemistry of the core constituents of

TABLE 2-VARIATIONS IN THE ¹³C ISOTOPIC ABUNDANCE (δ)* IN THE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS OF MAHARASA-MINERALS AND IN STONE-PEBBLES (Gt)**

Compd no	Origin of maharasa and stone-pebbles			Reference standard ^a
	Sh	Rm	Gt	
2a	11 80	8 82	10 21	0 03
5a	5 66	5 70	7 22	0 01
5b	5 55	4 82	8 91	0 01
6a,b	6 02	3 88	-	-

*For expression see text, (-) not determined

**Sh = *Shilajit* (Kumaon), Rm = (rajat-*Makshika*, Bihar), Gt = Gangotri-glacier till

^aFrom Ref 11

humus of terrestrial, aquatic, and arboreal origins^{2,7,10}. The evidence obtained from recent studies suggests abiotic origin of the low M_w compounds, at least partly. Thus, the isotopic (¹³C) abundance data of the low M_w organic compounds, isolated from the glacier-till (minerals) and the *maharasa*-humus (Table 2), suggest their non-photosynthetic route of formation. Due to strict discretionary control of plants in respect of use of ¹³C/¹²C in carbon dioxide during photosynthesis, the ratio is fixed in the resultant compounds derived by photosynthesis¹¹. The isotopic abundance factor of the low M_w organic compounds of humus and the till is expressed as $\delta^{13}C$ and calculated from the expression⁷,

$$\delta^{13}C = \left[\frac{^{13}C : ^{12}C \text{ of test sample}}{^{13}C : ^{12}C \text{ of reference}} - 1 \right] \times 10^2$$

The values (Table 2) were obtained from mass spectro-metric determinations of pulled-out carbons (as CO₂) and from ¹³C nmr of the respective compounds. The results clearly suggest that biotic synthesis (photosynthesis) may not be the only route for the genesis of these organic molecules (Table 2). Abiotic synthesis of these compounds, conceivably, on clay mineral surface would suit the scheme of primordial organic chemistry (*vide infra*). The following additional evidence lends credence to this postulate. Electron spin resonance (esr) analysis of the humic substances of *Shilajit*, *Makshika* and *ex-till* consistently exhibited an esr line of 5 ± 2 gauss width at g, 2.003 ± 0.00025 , indicating the presence of stable phenolic free radicals. Some of these free radicals have persisted in the humic polymers, being protected from the onslaughts of the macroenvironment, by intimate association with metal ions and clay min-

erals. They survive within the micropores of the humus/minerals and inhabit apparently for geological time (over 10^8 years).

The inverse relationship^{7,8} of the light absorption ratio at λ 465/665 (nm) (E_4/E_6) and the observed significantly lower values of the *till*-humus (E_4/E_6 of FAs) suggest still older origin of the *till*-humus in comparison to those of *Shilajit* and *Makshika*.

Chemical proof in support of the abiotic synthesis of the organic molecules was obtained. An hydro-aromatic intermediate (Fig. 1, str. 8), with higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value than is permitted by photosynthesis, was isolated from the inner-core of a *Shilajit* paleohumus⁷. The intermediate is conceivably derived from acetate-malonate (Scheme 2, str. 1a, b) by Diels-Alder type reaction. The intermediate, on keeping under laboratory conditions was converted into oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones (str. 5a, b) among other products⁷.

Maharajas and microorganism association

The *maharasa* minerals in their natural habitats are commonly found infested with microorganisms like extremophiles and archaeobacteria^{3,12}. These microorganisms perform several key roles in the maintenance and growth of living organisms and equilibrium of the macro-environment. The actions include synthesis and stability of humus⁷⁻⁹. Some species of archaeobacteria assume dormant forms and can survive extremely hostile and unfavourable living conditions, e.g. drying, heating, acidic pH, which are prevalent in the natural habitats of *maharasa* minerals. These microorganisms are ordinarily very inert metabolically. However, under congenial conditions, archaeobacteria (e.g. *Sulfolobus* and *Thermoplasma*) can synthesize organic ligands¹³ which form strong complexes with metal ions and clay minerals. Such structures (6 and 7) constitute the epitome of *maharajas*¹⁴. Additionally, both *maharajas* and extremophiles contain several uncommon organic compounds^{2,4,7,9,13}, such as poly- β -hydroxybutyrate, phenoxyethanol (str. 9), benzothiazole (str. 10) and isoprenoid-ether lipids. The origin of these molecules cannot be any external source and their existence seems to date back to geological time.

Since there are millions of possible compounds of comparable size and energy, a pertinent question arises as to why nature, through its primitive agents, has selected these particular ones for the evolutionary purpose? The question has been addressed and reasonable answers obtained. These molecules played a key role in the growth and propagation of the primitive organisms. Firstly, they supplied the chemical elements (C, S, N) out of which the organisms built their bodies; secondly, these organic molecules constituted a part of the enzyme system (osmo-enzymes) which the primitive organisms utilized for bioenergetics; thirdly, the

organic molecules promoted and maintained chemical equilibrium by acting as 'memory molecules' which backed the transfer of ambient energy^{2,7,14} to the primitive organisms; fourthly, the organic molecules being phenolic in nature maintained the environmental pH and thereby ensured the stability of the metal ion conjugation and the concomitant biochemical equilibrium of the primitive organisms; and finally, because these molecules confer stability to proteins under extreme conditions (e.g. high heat) and act in tandem with proteins by being part of some of the bio-catalytic centres¹⁵, their natural selection is comprehensible. Incidentally, a major issue relating to the extreme-ophiles concerns the stability of their macromolecules such as proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids under extreme environmental conditions³. This phenomenon appears also to be related to the stability of the low M_w organic compounds (ligands) found in the incinerated *maharajas* (*maharasa-bhasmas* in Sanskrit)¹⁶.

Incinerated *maharajas*, stability of organic ligands

According to Ayurveda, *maharajas* should be purified and then appropriately formulated for producing the desired therapeutic effects. The complete process involves several stages : (i) *sodhana* (purification from adherent impurities and toxic metal ions), (ii) *bhavna* (trituration with selected herbal ingredients, primarily to reduce the transition metal ions to their lower valency state(s)¹, and (iii) *putapaka* (repeated roasting/incineration at high temperature (600–800°, for several hours). These treatments are believed to transform the metal ions in the parent inorganic minerals to their lower valency state(s), in a colloidal form. These colloidal metal-*rasayanas* (panacea) are considered¹ to augment the bio-availability of the metal ions. Ghosal *et al.*¹⁶ chemically examined these *bhasmas*, procured from reputed herbal drug manufacturers and found that they were not simply metal ions but constituted of a host of organic compounds. Subsequently, Ghosal *et al.* prepared *Abhraka*, *Rasaka* and *Makshika-bhasmas*, according to the Ayurvedic texts¹ and analyzed them. Comprehensive chromatographic (hplc, hplc, gc) and spectroscopic (atomic absorption, nmr, gc-ms, esr) analyses of the commercial *bhasmas* and those prepared in the laboratory showed some striking similarities in respect of their lipids, phenolic compounds, fulvic acids (FAs), humic acids (HAs), humins (HMs), and proteins, in association with several metal ions^{2,6,15,16}. The low M_w phenolic compounds comprised hydroxyacetophenones (str. 3), oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones (str. 5), and N- and S-containing heterocyclic compound (str. 10). The E_4/E_6 (light absorption at λ 465/665 nm) ratios and the esr profiles of the *bhasmas* remained unaltered from those of the parent *maharasa* minerals. The humic substances containing free radicals as integral parts

of their molecules not only survived the geological processes of metabolism and coalification without loss of the free radicals, they have also survived the heat of incineration (preparation of *bhasmas*). This suggests that post-depositional chemical or physical modifications would not destroy the aromatic semiquinonoid properties of these compounds. The semiquinone free radicals present in the humus components of the *bhasmas* accomplish the energy transfer process by forming intermolecular charge transfer systems. That is, systems consisting of quinone groups of one polymeric chain situated close to hydroquinone groups of an adjacent chain. Intramolecular reactions of this kind are also possible (strs. 6a, b, Fig. 2). The heat stability of the organic molecules contained in the *maharasa-bhasmas* could be linked to that of the extremophiles associated with the *maharasa*-minerals in their natural habitats. This property appears to be acquired by a specific combination of structural stabilization factors, rather than by some general molecular design. Crystalline cell surface layers (*S*-layers) composed of planar assemblies of proteins or glycoproteins are one of the most commonly observed cell envelop structures of bacteria and archaea¹⁷. The *S*-layer structures can provide the organism with a selection advantage by functioning as a protective coat. A specific stabilization of these macromolecules against extraneous stresses may be achieved by conjugation and complexation with chaperons such as the metal ions and the polar heads of humus (Fig. 3). This combined association would provide extreme thermo-tolerance by protein-folding and by inner layer formation of the contained liposomes. The presence of such ion-pair network, clustered at both domain and sub-unit interfaces, serves as the main stabilizing factor of the organo-*maharasa* mineral complexes. Chemical analogy has been provided by synthesizing the vesicles of a model lipid, with phytanyl chains that mimicks tetra-ether lipids of archaebacteria. These lipids retained their integrity and also protected the co-habiting low M_w compounds when exposed to harsh conditions¹⁸. A distinct sequence of adaptation, leading to heat-stability of the organo-*maharasa* mineral complexes is indicated. The following additional evidence lends credence to this postulate. Oxygen uptake by the effector proteins is probably accompanied by the concomitant release of anionic ligands (Table 3). The released ligands, in turn, reduce the heat released upon oxygen binding of proteins and thereby contribute to lower the overall enthalpy change of the oxygenation reaction. This lowering of enthalpy constitutes a key factor in the longevity of biological species^{15,16}. In consonance with this postulate, the dielectric properties of the PMMA (polymethylmethacrylate)-*maharasa* humus conjugates exhibited high loss values (tan δ) compared to that of the control (PMMA-SO₃⁻ complex)¹⁹. This finding suggests greater electromagnetic insulation of

Fig. 3. Heat-stable organic complex from incinerated *maharasas* : (a) = metabolically inactive spores of extremophiles/archaea attached to clay minerals, (b) = transition metal ion/Fe-Cu-protein clusters, (c) = polar head of metallo-humate complex, (d) = lipid bilayers of microorganisms, and (e) = voids in humato-mineral complexes encaging primitive organic compounds.

the *maharasa*-humus complex ring-layer system(s) (Fig. 3). The concomitant protection of the encaged low M_w compounds against extraneous stress is, therefore, a distinct possibility. In a similar way, the low M_w compounds (strs. 3-5, 10) within the stone-pebbles (collected from the Gangotri-glacier *till*) find ecological niche and remain extant for ages. Clay minerals of about colloidal dimensions can constitute beautifully organized two-dimensional polymers, usually stacked on top of each other, sometimes folded into vesicles. They can form chelates and intercalates with

* TABLE 3—COMMON ORGANIC LIGANDS* OF MAHARASA-MINERAL COMPLEXES**

Maharasa mineral	Phenolic acids and heterocyclics	Hydroxyacetophenones	Oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones
<i>Makshika</i>			
Iron pyrite	2a-c, 9, 10	3a-c, 9, 10	5a,b
Chalcopyrite	2a-c, 9, 10	3a-c, 9, 10	5a,b
<i>Abhraka</i>			
Biotite	2a-c	3a-c	5a,b
Muscovite	2a,b	3a-c	5a,b
<i>Rasaka</i>			
Calamine	2a	3a	5a,b
Willemite	2a-c	3a-c	5a,b
<i>Shilajit</i>	2a-c	3a-c	5a-c, 6, 8, 9, 10

*Detected by hptlc analyses and reflectance spectra using makers; hplc using photodiode array detector and gc-ms analyses.

**The organic compounds were also isolated from the corresponding incinerated *maharasas* (*bhasmas*).

small organic molecules and can also catalyze a number of organic reactions²⁰.

The isolation and identification of a large number and variety of 'common' organic compounds (Table 3) from the different types of inorganic *maharasa*-minerals and also from the *till* (Gangotri-glacier) of a primitive era, support the notion that minerals are prevital agents that catalyze the synthesis of organic building blocks of 'metabolons'. Metabolons are considered as organized chemical entities that are capable of growth and metabolism²¹. During the final stage of pedogenesis, colloidal particles which are formed due to weathering, humification, and mineralization, accumulate and aggregate into crums and concretions. Colloidal humus particles in contact with inorganic minerals form polymeric complexes by way of electrochemical bonding and stabilize by cementing. During this process, the low M_w organic compounds that are generated, are absorbed within and the surface layers of the clay-humus complex polymers. *In situ*, these organic compounds serve as the organic material source for propagation and growth of rhizospheric microorganisms, e.g. extremophiles and archaea. The attendant assembly assumes a stable molecular architecture (of the type Fig. 3) where the living and non-living coexist for ages.

Conclusion

The evidence and speculations presented here tend to project the *mahararas* as the repository of primordial organic chemistry.

The data obtained support the ubiquitous occurrence of the oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones and their oligomers (strs. 5-7) in the *maharasa*-minerals. The complex assembly is stable and fends off all sorts of chemical and physical stresses to keep the contained low M_w organic compounds extant for ages. A remarkable feature of the oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones (strs. 5 and 6) is their occurrence also in the organ deposits and in secretions, and excretions of a large number of mammals and insects. But, surprisingly, these compounds have rarely been encountered in photosynthetic plants. This phenomenon suggests their alternative (biological/abiological) route of formation, other than photosynthesis. These phenolic compounds have been isolated from the renal calculi of Western and South-Australian sheep (clover-stone), in the stomachs of apes and goats and from the scent glands of Canadian beaver, from the faeces of Ladakhian mouse, and from the haemolymph gland of several insects (e.g. termites), and from the kidney and gall-stone of man^{15,16}.

The remarkable co-occurrence of the oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones (and their oligomers) in the living organisms and in *mahararas* (which serve as the source of *rasayana* to living organisms) may constitute a vital link

of ascension of the non-living to the living. As expected, these molecules constitute the major bioactive principles of the *mahararas*^{14-16,22}.

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